

Review of UK NSC rapid reviews (evidence summaries) and updating the UK NSC rapid review guidance

Protocol

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Plain Language Summary

What is the problem? The UK National Screening Committee (UK NSC) uses quick research summaries (called rapid reviews) to make decisions about health screening. They want to make sure these summaries are carried out consistently and to a high standard. It's worth noting that the UK NSC first created guidelines for their rapid reviews about ten years ago, after the government's health committee suggested it in 2014.

What will we do? Our project aims to look at some past summaries and to compare them to the most up-to-date advice on how to summarise research rapidly. This advice was written by a trusted group called Cochrane, an independent, global network of researchers and healthcare professionals who work together to produce high-quality, reliable health information to help people make informed decisions about health. They are experts in review methods.

How will we do this? In the first part of the project, our team will carefully choose a variety of past UK NSC summaries. These will be on different health topics, and created by different research teams. We will check these summaries against the Cochrane advice to see what was done well and what could be improved. This will help us understand if the current way of doing things is working well, and where there might be inconsistencies between different reviews.

Secondly, we will use what we have learned from looking at the previous evidence summaries to update the UK NSC guidelines that are written for research teams who do rapid reviews. We will use new advice from Cochrane and make the guidelines clearer and easier to follow. We will also update the template that is used to write the summaries and create a new checklist to help make sure future summaries are of high quality.

How will the findings be used? Ultimately, this project will help the UK NSC make sure their rapid reviews are reliable and based on the latest, most trusted methods. This will lead to clearer and more consistent evidence being used for making important decisions about health screening in the UK.

How will the public be involved in the project? Our patient and public representatives will input to communication and dissemination of our work; for example, through production of plain language summaries.

Background

The UK National Screening Committee (UK NSC), serving as the central advisory body for population screening programmes across the four UK nations, relies heavily on synthesised evidence to formulate its policy recommendations. Within this evidence-to-policy pathway, the UK NSC established internal guidance for the conduct of rapid reviews approximately a decade ago. This initiative was a direct response to recommendations issued by the House of Commons Select Committee on Health in 2014, which underscored the critical need for robust, consistent, and transparent evidence synthesis to underpin national health policy decisions. The

primary objective of this original guidance was to enhance the methodological consistency and rigour of these rapid reviews, recognising their role in the broader evidence aggregation process informing national screening policy development.

Rapid reviews represent an expedited approach to evidence synthesis, designed to provide timely answers to pressing health policy and clinical questions while maintaining methodological rigour. Unlike full systematic reviews, which aim for exhaustive identification of all relevant evidence, comprehensive data extraction, and risk of bias assessment, rapid reviews typically streamline or omit certain systematic review processes to expedite completion. This differentiation often manifests in a narrower scope, a more constrained search strategy (e.g., limiting databases or publication types), fewer reviewers involved in screening and data extraction, and a more pragmatic approach to quality appraisal or risk of bias assessment. The inherent trade-off lies between rigour, comprehensiveness and timeliness; rapid reviews are fit-for-purpose when decisions are time-sensitive, and a complete systematic review is not feasible or necessary, yet a structured evidence synthesis is still paramount.

The UK NSC evidence review process [1] generally begins with an “evidence map” which provides a quick overview of the “volume and type” of evidence on a topic. If there is sufficient evidence to warrant further assessment, a rapid review or “evidence summary” may be conducted. The UK NSC label their rapid reviews as “evidence summaries” and this term will be used throughout this protocol when referring to UK NSC rapid reviews. Evidence summaries assess the “volume, type and direction” of the evidence on a topic. For the UK NSC, evidence summaries serve as a focused assessment of the evidence landscape for specific screening questions. They inform the feasibility and necessity of more in-depth analyses, identify key evidence gaps, and provide a foundational understanding of the clinical effectiveness, harms, and cost-effectiveness of potential screening interventions.

A retrospective case report published in 2019 [2] provided an initial, albeit limited, empirical evaluation of a single UK NSC evidence summary. This assessment systematically applied several established methodological checklists, including AMSTAR 2, PRISMA, and Kaltenthaler's checklist [3-5], frameworks often adapted from or primarily designed for systematic reviews. The findings generally affirmed the methodological soundness of the evaluated evidence summary within the pragmatic confines of rapid review methodologies. However, the report concurrently identified specific areas where greater methodological detail and transparency could be beneficial, particularly when frameworks designed for comprehensive systematic reviews were applied to a rapid synthesis. Consequently, the report advocated for a more expansive and systematic assessment of the UK NSC's broader portfolio of evidence summaries, ideally leveraging a validated checklist specifically tailored for rapid review methodologies to identify consistent patterns of strengths and areas for improvement across multiple syntheses.

In 2024, the Cochrane Collaboration, a globally recognised authority in evidence synthesis methodology, released updated and refined recommendations for the conduct of rapid reviews [6]. To ensure continuous quality improvement, methodological alignment with contemporary

best practices, and the continued relevance of its evidence products, the UK NSC intends to undertake a comprehensive assessment of a selected sample of its existing evidence summaries against these recent Cochrane recommendations. This comparative assessment is designed to provide empirical data that will not only highlight strengths, but also inconsistencies in practice, and areas for improvement to critically inform the subsequent updating and renewal of the current UK NSC guidance for conducting evidence summaries. The overarching project is strategically phased into two distinct, yet interconnected, components: an initial rigorous methodological assessment of existing UK NSC evidence summaries, followed by the systematic development and refinement of updated evidence summary guidance.

Aims & Objectives

This project aims to update the UK NSC guidance for conducting evidence summaries.

The project will be conducted in two phases, with the following objectives:

Phase 1: Assessment of Existing UK NSC Evidence Summaries

- To identify a representative sample of existing evidence summaries commissioned by the UK NSC, ensuring diversity in topic and evidence review team (supplier).
- To evaluate the selected sample of previous evidence summaries against the updated Cochrane rapid review methods guidance (2024) [6].
- To identify areas of strength, inconsistencies in practice, and areas where improvements can be made in the UK NSC's current practices.

Phase 2: Development of Updated UK NSC Guidance for Evidence Summaries

- To revise the UK NSC guidance for conducting evidence summaries by incorporating findings from Phase 1 and updated methodology recommendations from the Cochrane guidance.
- To update the document template for UK NSC evidence summaries.
- To develop an updated reporting checklist for UK NSC evidence summaries.

Methods

The project will be conducted in two phases, employing the following methods:

Phase 1: Assessment of Existing Evidence Summaries

1. **Sampling Strategy:**
 - Review the list of eligible evidence summaries provided (Table 2 in the project brief).
 - Use a stratified sampling approach to select 15 evidence summaries from the 45 provided by the UK NSC, ensuring representation across key categories, and providers. The selection of 15 evidence summaries should be sufficient for identification of patterns and variations, whilst remaining feasible within the project

timescale. The stratification will consider the following criteria:

- **Topic Area:** To capture the range of screening topics.
 - **Target population:** (e.g., antenatal, newborn, child, adult).
 - **Supplier Organisation:** To ensure representation from different suppliers.
 - **Year:** To assess how practice may have changed over time.
- In discussion with UK NSC, a sample of 15 evidence summaries (one third of the total number of summaries conducted) has been selected as an appropriate sample size. This sample should be large enough to allow for meaningful analysis and identification of patterns and variations, but feasible within project resources. After the assessment of the 15 evidence summaries selected, we will discuss with the UK NSC whether this has given enough representative information or if we need to review any further evidence summaries regarding specific issues and approaches.
 - Document the rationale for the sampling strategy, including the chosen stratification variables and the justification for the sample size.
 - If there are fewer than 5 different suppliers, all suppliers will be included. If there are more than 5, a random sample will be selected.

2. Evaluation Framework:

- The primary evaluation framework will be the updated Cochrane rapid review methods guidance (2024) [6].
- The Cochrane guidance will be the primary focus for Phase 1 of the review; however, key items from wider rapid review guidance (from other sources, see Speckemeier et al 2022 [7] for example) may be included if not covered by the Cochrane guidance. Other systematic review risk of bias tools (such as AMSTAR-2 and ROBIS) and reporting guidelines (such as PRISMA and interim guidance on PRISMA-RR) will also be checked for any additional key items relevant to rapid reviews.
- Develop a structured data extraction form based on the Cochrane guidance (and additional methods guidance if applicable). This form will cover key aspects of the rapid review process, including:
 - Clarity of objectives and review question(s) (e.g., structured around the PICO framework or equivalent)
 - Search strategy (e.g., number of databases searched, which sources (including grey literature), search limits applied, reported peer-review of search strings, supplementary searching)
 - Study selection criteria (e.g., inclusion, exclusion, languages, geographical settings) and process (e.g., pilot screen of a sample, double-screening and %)
 - Data extraction methods (e.g., piloting and data checking)
 - Assessment of methodological quality/risk of bias of included studies (tool used, application, and reporting).
 - Data synthesis methods (type of synthesis, inclusion of meta-analysis or justification otherwise, how existing systematic reviews included in synthesis)
 - Assessment of certainty of evidence (e.g., GRADE).
 - Reporting of limitations of the rapid review process.

- Adherence to any reporting guidelines.
- Documentation of deviations from protocol or planned methods.
- Evidence summary authors' own descriptions of the strengths, limitations and challenges of their methods (where reported)
- Time taken to conduct review (UK NSC will provide this information)
- For each evidence summary, each item in the data extraction form will be assessed as either Met, Partially met, Not met or not reported, or Not applicable. In addition, brief narrative details (pre-specified) will be extracted for each item, where applicable.
- The draft evaluation framework / data extraction form will be shared with the UK NSC and the Project Advisory Group for this project to check that it covers all items relevant to UK NSC evidence summaries.

3. **Data Extraction:**

- Pilot the application of the evaluation framework / data extraction (based on the Cochrane rapid review methods guidance [6]) on two evidence summaries, and check consistency across the project team.
- Data will be extracted from each evidence summary by a member of the project team, and key data will be checked by another member, to ensure consistency across the review team.

4. **Analysis:**

- Conduct a descriptive analysis of the extracted data to:
 - Briefly describe the characteristics of the included evidence summaries (for example, topic area, population, supplier).
 - Summarise which items were most commonly met, partially met, or not met/not reported, across the sampled evidence summaries, together with reasons and justifications where reported.
 - Assess the degree of adherence to the Cochrane rapid review guidance (plus items from other guidance, where applicable),
 - Identify common practices, variations, omissions and inconsistencies in the conduct and reporting of the reviews.
 - Create a summary table to summarise key findings about which criteria were commonly/rarely/never met, categorised by themes (such as clarity of review question, search methods, risk of bias assessment). This can provide a link from the key findings to the development of specific recommendations for the updated evidence summary guidance.
 - Through discussion with the UK NSC and the Project Advisory Group, identify which items should be consistently conducted/reported in evidence summaries, and which items might be recommended as optional depending on the review context and evidence base (the latter may include, for example, use of meta-analysis). This will inform Phase 2 (updating guidance for evidence summaries).

Phase 2: Development of Updated UK NSC Guidance

The findings from Phase 1 will be used to revise the existing UK NSC guidance for evidence summaries. The project advisory group will be involved in this process by providing feedback on the draft documents.

1. Updating the Evidence Summary Process Document:

The revision process will:

- Consider relevant recommendations from the Cochrane rapid review guidance (plus items from other guidance, where applicable).
- Address the areas for improvement identified in Phase 1, providing specific and actionable guidance. As noted above, this will likely involve discussion with the UK NSC and the Project Advisory Group, to identify which items should be consistently conducted/reported in evidence summaries, and which items might be recommended as optional depending on the review context and evidence base (the latter may include, for example, use of meta-analysis)
- Ensure the updated guidance is clear, concise, practical, and tailored to the needs of those conducting evidence summaries for the UK NSC.
- Consider the resource implications of implementing the new guidance.

2. Template Update:

The revision process will:

- Review the current template for UK NSC evidence summaries.
- Update the template to align with the revised process document, ensuring it facilitates the complete and transparent reporting of all essential elements of a UK NSC evidence summary.
 - Consider formatting and structure.
 - Ensure it promotes clarity and ease of use - the project advisory group and UK NSC will be consulted regarding these aspects.

3. Reviewing the UK NSC Reporting Checklist for Evidence Summaries:

- Review the current reporting checklist, and update it if and where required to ensure it is:
 - Informed by the findings of Phase 1 and the revised UK NSC template.
 - Comprehensive, covering all critical aspects of a rigorous evidence summary.
 - Clear, concise, and easy to use.
 - Aligned with the updated UK NSC guidance.

Outputs

The project will deliver the following outputs:

- **Phase 1 Output:** A comprehensive report summarising the results of the review of the existing evidence summaries. This report will include:
 - A description of the sampling strategy and the characteristics of the included evidence summaries.
 - An analysis of the alignment of current practices with the Cochrane rapid review guidance.
 - Identification of areas of strength and weaknesses in current practices.
 - Specific examples from the assessed summaries to illustrate areas for improvement.
 - Recommendations for revising the UK NSC guidance.

Following delivery of the report to NSC, we propose a discussion of the potential for publishing the report as a working paper or in an academic journal.

- **Phase 2 Outputs:**
 - **Updated UK NSC Guidance (Process Document) for Evidence Summaries:** A revised document providing clear, comprehensive, and up-to-date guidance on conducting evidence summaries for the UK NSC.
 - **Updated Template for UK NSC Evidence Summaries:** A revised template to facilitate the implementation of the updated guidance and ensure complete and transparent reporting.
 - **Updated Checklist for UK NSC Evidence Summaries:** A tailored reporting checklist for future UK NSC evidence summaries, aligned with the updated guidance and best practices in rapid review methodology.

Project team

The project team will include:

Project Lead: Anthea Sutton

Deputy Lead: Dr Katy Cooper

Project Team:

- Anthea Sutton, Dr Katy Cooper, Sue Harnan and Abdullah Pandor, Gamze Nalbant (data extraction and analysis)
- Sarah Ren (statistical expertise if required)
- Researchers from the other ESGs will assist with data extraction and analysis where appropriate - Pooja Suresh Kumar (University of Warwick) & Issie Hazell (University of Bristol)

The project team will meet regularly to ensure consistency of understanding and processes.

Project Advisory Group

A project advisory group will be set up, consisting of members of the wider SENSS group and 1-2 members of each of the other two Screening ESGs. Relevant external stakeholders (with expertise in evidence synthesis, rapid review methodology and/or the UK NSC context) may be invited to join the group subject to agreement from NSC.

The project advisory group will be consulted at key points in the process including:

- Development of the protocol
- Designing of the data extraction form
- Reviewing the draft of the Phase 1 (assessment of existing evidence summaries) report
- Development of the updated UK NSC Guidance (Phase 2) including the revised process document, template and checklist
- Dissemination of the project and its outcomes.

Members of the project advisory group:

Professor Andrew Booth (University of Sheffield)

Dr Fiona Campbell (Honorary Staff Member, University of Sheffield)

Mark Clowes (University of Sheffield)

Dr Joanna Leaviss (University of Sheffield)

Dr Anna Mae Scott (University of Warwick)

Dr Christopher Stinton (University of Warwick)

Professor Penny Whiting (University of Bristol)

Shona Kirtley (University of Bristol)

Timelines

Timelines for Phase 1 Assessment of existing evidence summaries are provided in the table below. The timelines for Phase 2 will be agreed with the NSC team following delivery of the Phase 1 report.

Task	Date
Initial meeting	2 April 2025
Form project team	30 April
Draft protocol	9 May
Invite colleagues to join the project advisory group	16 May
Share the protocol with the project advisory group	16 May
Protocol to UK NSC for feedback	25 July
Feedback from UK NSC and revisions to the protocol if required	September 2025
Meeting with UK NSC	October 2025
Revisions to protocol	October 2025
Circulate final protocol to project advisory group & UK NSC for final comments/approval	October 2025
Finalise the sampling strategy and select the sample of evidence summaries	October 2025
Develop and pilot the data extraction form, including checking guidance documents for relevant items	Mid November 2025
Circulate and agree data extraction form with project advisory group & UK NSC	November to December 2025
Conduct data extraction from the selected evidence summaries (including data checking by a third reviewer)	31 May 2026
Data analysis and synthesis of findings	31 July 2026
Update project advisory group (meeting)	July-August 2026
Draft Phase 1 report	30 September 2026
Feedback from NSC	Mid October 2026
Final Phase 1 Report summarising the assessment results and recommendations delivered to NSC	October 2026
Phase 1 meeting with NSC & propose timelines for Phase 2	October 2026
Start of Phase 2: Updating the Evidence Summary process document, template and checklist	October to November 2026

References

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